

Assessing the Role of Entrepreneurship Training in the Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Zambia: A Case of Chongwe District

Francis Ndhlovu

MSc In Project Management candidate

The Copperbelt University, P.O. Box 21692, Kitwe, Zambia, Jumbo Drive, Riverside

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to assess the role of entrepreneurship training in the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Zambia. The study sought answer to the following three questions: i) Are SMEs aware of trainings conducted in the area? ii) What types of training are being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs? iii) What is the influence of training programs on business growth of SMES in Chongwe district?

The study used a quantitative research design and purposive sampling technique was used to recruit n = 100 and SMEs and Key informant (KI).

Males dominated the gender distribution in the sample, with n = 84 (84.0%) outnumbering females n = 16 (16.0 %). The ages of individuals who were (25 to 34) and (35 to 44) n = 46 were very evenly distributed (46.0 %). Because most respondents lack a strong academic background, they do not conduct their business professionally. More than half of those polled, n = 80 (88.9%), were ignorant of any entrepreneurial training programs in the area, compared to n = 11 (11.0%) who were. A considerable proportion of SMEs n = 80 (88.9%) were unaware of this form of training, whereas only n = 10 (11.1%) were aware. The study discovered that nearly all the KI and SMEs in the sample n = 97 (97.0%) believed that entrepreneurship training programs influenced SMEs' business a little larger and a lot larger, while a small percentage believed there was no difference n = 2 (2.0%) and a small percentage believed it contributed a little smaller n = 1 (1.0%).

To successfully reach out to all SMEs in the town and distant areas, awareness initiatives and well-established communication methods are required.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneur, Growth, Small and Medium Enterprise (SME), Key informant (KI) and quantitative research design.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background of the study

According to Zambia Development Agency, (2017) until 1991, Zambia was largely run by the public companies (parastatals). Following liberalization, the country's attention turned to the private sector. This opening of the economy into a market economy ushered in the growth in the number of SMEs spanning many sectors. There has since been an increase in the number of registered SMEs in the country with still a large proportion of them operating as unregistered businesses and lacking entrepreneurship training. The major areas of concentration for the Zambian SMEs include services, retailing,

agriculture, small-scale mining, transport, education, hospitality and food, tourism, transport, technical skills and technology, among others, (Zambia Invest, 2017).

According to the National Micro and Small Enterprise Baseline Survey in Zambia, (1999), SMEs are the driving force behind the economy. Data from the Ministry of Commerce and Trade indicates that this sector provides employment to over 2 million of the Zambian workforces and contributes to about 18.4% of the GDP. The importance of entrepreneurial training as one of the ingredients of SMES growth has globally been recognized.

There is a significant impact on participant's characteristics and final participation outcomes after training (Edgomb, 2002). Entrepreneurs are able to acquire better management techniques, expand their enterprises, adopt new technology and build more business linkages.

The Zambia Invest (2017) argues that entrepreneurship training improves the quality as well. However, SMEs in Zambia have been said to report high rates of failures with many of the enterprises dying at an infant stage. Among other reasons for the SMES' failure is the lack of entrepreneurial training. This has significantly contributed to lack of business growth which in turn has resulted to the inability of SMES to contributing to Zambia's GDP growth as expected. Therefore, this study aims at assessing the role of entrepreneurship training to SMEs growth in Chongwe district.

1.1 Statement of the problem

According to Oteri, et al (2015) academics, practitioners and governments worldwide increasingly recognized the role of entrepreneurship training in providing entrepreneurs with the necessary business skills and acumen to plan, set up and grow their business ideas. This is because according to the human capital theory, investment in knowledge, skills and the abilities enhance the productive capacity, competencies to engage in a more enterprising, innovative and flexible manner in a changing workplace environment (Becker, 1964). SMEs in Zambia do significantly contribute to the country's economic growth through employment creation, poverty reduction, and they act as intermediaries in trade (GOK, 2014). However, despite the critical role played by the sector, it is faced with many challenges which make over 90% of the SMEs not to see their third birthday. Nearly four out of five SMEs in Zambia fail within the first few months of operation (Kamunge, et al, 2014). This high failure rate is mainly attributed to lack of skilled workforce and stiff competition in the market (Okpara, (2015). This has been blamed on the entrepreneurs lacking the entrepreneurship skills to steer their business to growth.

To address these challenges, the Zambian Government and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) has been trying to be established entrepreneurship trainings to provide SME with technical and business skills. These entrepreneurship trainings are intended to enable the SMEs acquire unique human resource capabilities for competitive advantage (Mungai, 2012; Sambo, Gichira, & Yusuf, 2015). However, there is lacks sufficient of evidence on how far this initiative gone and the role played by the entrepreneurship training, including the needs assessment, content of training and method of training as well as the benefits of entrepreneurship training on performance and growth of SMEs in Zambia. In addition, information gaps make smaller firms less aware of the benefits they would obtain from training, and few see training as a strategic tool (Kolstad et al. 2009). Due to higher turnover in employees, small firms may not realize the same benefits from training investments as larger firms. Several researchers have also identified that training practices in SMEs have not received significant attention in research; they further stress the need for future studies on this issue. This necessitates the purpose of this study to assess the role of entrepreneurship training in the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Zambia: a case of Chongwe District.

1.2 Aim of the study

The aim of this study is to assess the role of entrepreneurship training in the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Zambia, a case of Chongwe District.

1.2.1 Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study intends to:

- i. To identify the types of entrepreneurship training being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs?
- ii. To establish if SMEs are aware of the trainings conducted in the area
- iii. To establish how training programs influences business growth of SMES in Chongwe district.

1.3 Research Questions

The study sought answer to the following three questions:

- i. What types of training are being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs?
- ii. Are SMEs aware of trainings conducted in the area?
- iii. What is the influence of training programs on business growth of SMES in Chongwe district?

1.4 Significance of the Research

To begin, undertaking this study will greatly be contributing to the understanding of the critical role skills training can contribute to SMEs growth especially that other options such as financing has been tried but the fruits are still not positive and sustainable.

Further, the research will contribute to the existing knowledge about the contributions of entrepreneurship training to the SME sector, specifically in Chongwe. It will also be useful to anyone who intends to do similar studies in the future by examining other pertinent elements.

1.5 Limitations of the study

The study is anticipating three limitations, and these are:

The first is that because of COVID-19 pandemic respondents may have mixed feelings in welcoming the researcher for interviews for fear of contracting it.

Secondly, the literacy levels of the population in Chongwe district may compromise the study as they may not understand the significance of the study.

Thirdly, the skeptical of the respondents may also deteriorate the success of the study as planned by the Researcher.

1.6 Scope of the study

Delimitation of the study is defined by Orodho (2005) as the boundary limits of the study regions. This study limits itself to only SMEs operating in Chongwe district. Chongwe district is located in Lusaka province and has a population of 137, 461 people (CSO 2000). The targeted population will be SMEs in Chongwe District, registered under the Chongwe District Chambers of Commerce Trade and Industry.

1.7 Operational definitions

The researcher has offered a list of operational definitions in order to provide a better grasp of what the researcher was trying to convey to the readers. The following are some of the important terms that were used:

Entrepreneurship: is defined as the skill and willingness to create, organize, and manage a business enterprise while taking reasonable risks to profit. Nwafor (2007) defines entrepreneurship as an individual's willingness and aptitude to search out investment possibilities in each environment, as well as the capacity to effectively build and operate a business based on such opportunities. The phrases willingness, ability, and investment possibilities are crucial to understanding entrepreneurship in this definition. To put it another way, the entrepreneur must have the ability/technical know-how as well as the willingness to start a business.

Entrepreneur: An entrepreneur is a person who starts a business or a series of enterprises with the goal of generating a profit while taking financial risks.

Growth: In this study, growth was defined as having access to funds that allowed SMEs to develop from small to medium to large businesses.

Small and Medium Enterprise (SME): For this study, the term "SME" was defined according to (Pour) (2006). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have been classified as small or medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) based on the number of employees and the value of total fixed assets excluding land value. This is a more accurate description of Zambia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to summarize the researcher's review of the literature related to the topic at hand. By demonstrating familiarity with the body of knowledge and illustrating how the current study issue is connected to earlier

research, a literature review may help generate credibility (Neuman, 2006). In this chapter, the study's literature is reviewed. The review relied significantly on empirical research as well as data from acknowledged published sources such as books, online publications, and journals. It investigates various scholars' opinions on entrepreneurship training in relation to the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises, as well as their definitions and thoughts about SME's and the role they play in the economy. Entrepreneurship training and development has long been acknowledged as critical to the effective management of businesses, especially Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), on a global scale.

2.1 SMEs awareness of the Entrepreneurship trainings

One successful way to help SMEs expand, according to the Committee of Donor Agencies for Small Enterprise Development (2001), is to improve both their management and production abilities. Governments and donors have been engaged in the training field, typically through public training institutes and publicly financed trainers. However, they believe that these methods are insufficient to completely engage potential SMEs in entrepreneurship training.

According to research done in Brazil, there is a lack of communication between trainers and potential trainees (Anderson 2000). This resulted in a reduction in training awareness among SMEs all around the country. Trainers frequently indicate a wish to use the media but believe that media such as radio and newspapers are too expensive, according to FIT Resources Ltd (2002). Because marketing is inefficient, there are fewer trainees than there may have been, and trainers may have to charge more training costs as a result.

Strengthening SMEs' internal capacities has been a major focus in recent years, according to Ergas and Orr (2007), and is positioned as an alternative or complementary strategy for SME development. Training is widely acknowledged as a vital instrument for SMEs to build their internal skills.

However, research in Western nations has revealed that, while trainers, consultants, and policymakers regard training as a vital instrument for SME growth, SMEs themselves do not, and a large proportion of them are unaware of these trainings. In this context, we conducted a study in Bangalore (India) to determine the training needs of SMEs as they see them. A survey of 400 randomly chosen SME firms in Bangalore was undertaken. The poll asked about training awareness and preferences for subjects, duration, timings, pricing, and training providers, among other things. The findings suggest that SMEs' awareness levels are relatively low, and their training-related attitudes and behavior are not dissimilar to what Western researchers have seen (Ergas, and Orr 2007).

According to research performed in Zimbabwe by SIYB/ILO (2001), SMEs lose 65 percent of their market owing to their inability to link training to their enterprises. Trainers state in the survey that SMEs are often unaware that they have challenges in their operations. Those who manage SMEs, on the other hand, may believe that they know everything there is to know about their company, resulting in a lack of interest in the possible advantages of training.

A study in Uganda (Ntale and Mukasa, 2009) found that 160 small business owners and 89 medium business owners were aware of entrepreneurship training provided by the government in collaboration with NGOs and individual trainers, but they were unaware of who was eligible to participate or where the trainings were held.

In Kenya, 78 percent of individuals who had utilized training in the previous two years, whether through purchase or free offer, had done so more than twice. Other market research, aside from the Kenya scenario, indicates a similar tendency, namely, a low awareness rate, a low usage rate, and a high retention rate (Ibid).

Adebiyi, Banjo, and Regin explored entrepreneurship training for emerging SMEs in Nigeria (2017). According to the poll, only SME owners with a high level of education participated in government-sponsored training, while those without a high level of education did not participate due to a lack of interest or, in certain cases, a lack of expertise.

Mayuran (2016) did an empirical study in South Africa on the impact of entrepreneurship training on small company performance and discovered that small business owners do not participate in training programs due to a lack of information, since most of them are not taught. According to the report, there is a dearth of communication between training providers and small enterprises. They are unable to participate in government-sponsored and partner-sponsored entrepreneurship training programs because of this.

According to the UNDP (2004) study in Zambia found that the challenge in promoting entrepreneurship training is the notion of training itself. The study found that many SMEs have an informal network from which they get advice and information, which they do not regard as "training". In an extreme case, some SMEs resist the idea of participating in training as they think training is only for youth, not for adults. This is likely why, when a market survey of 300 SME

respondents was done in Zambia, just 17 of the respondents comprehended what was being asked about when it came to training-related topics. This is an example of the demand side of entrepreneurial education, which should be boosted. However, the market research shows that once SMEs attempt training, many of them become repeat customers.

2.2 Types of entrepreneurship training

Entrepreneurship training is well-known across the world, and many governments understand the importance of entrepreneurship training programs and their intended objectives in achieving the desired goals (Viviers et al, 2001; Monk, 2000).

The goals of entrepreneurial training, according to Nasrudin & Othman (2012), are to improve skills, develop a better knowledge of entrepreneurship, and produce more entrepreneurs. According to Kalamwati (2012), real-life activities should be included in the proper approaches for facilitating entrepreneurship training. Entrepreneurs, on the other hand, require experiential pedagogical interventions, according to Fredrick (2007).

Linan (2004) identified four types of entrepreneurial training that are commonly used to develop policy: To begin with, entrepreneurial awareness training should provide awareness to all SMEs and should not be limited to the creation of new ventures; rather, it should provide SMEs with options for developing the skills needed to assist them in deciding whether to pursue a career in entrepreneurship. SMEs benefit from this sort of opportunity since it broadens their knowledge and improves their business possibilities. Second, SMEs with the desire to start a new business should be offered entrepreneurship training. This sort of program is aimed at providing practical help to company start-ups while also ensuring the continued growth of SMEs' entrepreneurial abilities.

There are four forms of training available to entrepreneurs: 1) sensibilization (make sensitive or aware) for entrepreneurship – providing awareness education that focuses on increasing the number of people who have a motivation for, or who are sufficiently knowledgeable about, entrepreneurship to consider it important for their future. 2) entrepreneurship education – providing the development of entrepreneurial competencies and behaviors, including both hard and soft skills; 3) education for entrepreneurship – providing education that focuses on increasing the number of people who have a motivation for, or who are sufficiently knowledgeable about, entrepreneurship to consider it important for their future 4) education in entrepreneurship – Continuing business education for people who have previously started a business (Henry et al., 2005). (Henry et al., 2005; Davey, Hannon &Penaluna, 2016).

Trainers employ several methods of training to impart entrepreneurial information, skills, and attitudes to learners, according on the need or need. Entrepreneurs learn differently than other professions, according to research (Fredrick, 2007; Gatchalian, 2010). Learners require active and pedagogical interventions to deepen their learning in entrepreneurial theory, practice, and process (Fredrick, 2007). Studies have recommended a variety of entrepreneurship training options, including lectures, team teaching, group assignments, field tours or visits, business plans, case studies, problem-based learning, presentations, seminars or workshops, decision-making exercises, attachments, internships, consulting assignments, actual business operations, and research (Mansor & Othaman, 2011).

2.3 Influence of entrepreneurship training programs on growth of SMEs

In their search for fresh creative talent, SMEs and worldwide corporations are actively supporting the growth of entrepreneurship training (Volkman, Wilson, Mariotti, Rabuzzi, Vyakarnam, & Sepulveda, 2009). National governments and the European Commission have recognized entrepreneurship training as a source of income and jobs, while academics have agreed that entrepreneurship can be learnt, even though some of its parts are impacted by genetic predispositions (Nicolaou & Shane, 2011; Zhang, et al., 2009; Fayolle, 2007).

Entrepreneurship is recognized as a vital engine for economic growth and job creation, which is why scholars and professionals support entrepreneurial training (Wong et al., 2005). Entrepreneurial education is commonly viewed as a reaction to the more globalized, unpredictable, and complicated world we live in, which requires all people and organizations in society to be increasingly prepared with entrepreneurial skills (Gibb, 2002). Aside from the more common reasons for promoting entrepreneurship training, such as economic development and job creation, there is a growing emphasis on the effects entrepreneurial activities can have on SMEs' perceived relevancy, engagement, and motivation in both business and work life (Surlemont, 2007). (Amabile and Kramer, 2011).

Finally, entrepreneurship training has been positioned as a strategy of empowering people and organizations to produce social value for the public good (Rae, 2010). (Volkman et al., 2009, Austin et al., 2006).

The World Bank (2006) found that SMEs managed by educated managers and who teach their personnel outperformed others in all elements of company success, including having fewer labor-related issues, exporting, and seizing niches in marketplaces that are frequently characterized by intense rivalry (Levy et al, 2004). A company's success is determined by its resources, which include a solid organizational structure, cutting-edge technology, high-quality raw materials, and productive people resources.

Human resources are the most significant of these components since they oversee creating corporate policies, administering the financial system according to the scenario, and selecting the best marketing approach and plan for the organization (Babbie 2007:186). Employees must be well-trained and educated to properly perform their responsibilities and tasks in managing a company (Huang 2001). Huang (2001) also agreed that training may be a significant driving force in helping a company expand and enhance its capabilities, resulting in increased profitability.

Jones (2005), who studied the effects of training on business growth, found that SMEs that increased their training efforts saw an increase in sales and revenue growth. Small businesses provided training to all employees, not just manufacturing workers. According to Tan (1996), skills upgrading initiatives among senior management of African enterprises are critical, and they can contribute to increased productivity and customer satisfaction across the continent. Customers' loyalty, revenue growth, market share expansion, and demand increase might all result from the latter.

According to Hisrich and Peters (2001), training opens new options and possibilities, as well as a willingness to try and finish tasks in new ways. Entrepreneurial trainability is taken for granted in this study and is backed up by Gibb (2000), Kuratko, and Hodgetts (2001). Currently, the issues with entrepreneurship training may be evident in the lack of agreement on course content and curricula. Rosa and McAlpine (2002) bolster this claim by pointing out that there is a significant gap in the entrepreneurial training program where major standardized components exist. Their research also suggests that the complex and multi-disciplinary components of entrepreneurship should be given more attention in the training environment.

According to the Committee of Donor Agencies, a variety of business services such as training, consulting, marketing, information, business linkage promotion, and technical development can contribute to company success (2001). According to a survey performed by Geopoll (2015), just three out of ten Kenyans engaged in activities targeted at boosting their business in the previous year. According to the study, Kenyan youth feel that the government should focus more on teaching entrepreneurs rather than working with private businesses (Ochieng, 2015). According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM, 2007), access to entrepreneurial education and training is restricted, as is its usefulness.

Wasihum and Paul (2010) found that entrepreneurs with more entrepreneurial training in Ethiopia were better able to make sensible and reasonable decisions about firm management, resulting in SME development. According to Renny (2011), the World Bank, European Union, and UNDP funded MSE technology and training programs in company growth in conjunction with the Ministry of Planning on ongoing government and donor-supported projects, and some progress has been made. According to research by Moronge and Muiro (2013), partner-initiated initiatives contributed to the development and expansion of SMEs in Kenya, 43 percent of them benefitted from business advice. Training respondents evaluated 15 percent of programs as exceptional, 41 percent as very good, and 42 percent as good, according to the report. As a result, the study indicated that development partners contributed significantly to SME growth in Kenya through entrepreneurship training programs.

SMEs in developing countries in general and in Zambia lack the managerial skills and entrepreneurship training to effectively conduct their business and to deal with the cumbersome legal and regulatory framework, (World Bank 2006). Asian (2009) entrepreneurship skills training were the critical success factors of all businesses, and small business was no exception. This is true because when entrepreneurship skills are lacking in an enterprise, it exerts significant challenges on SME development. The scarcity of management talent in many developing countries has a profound impact on SMEs and hampers the progress of their development. This is common especially the new and inexperienced SMEs who may not have the required skills and managerial capacity to fully exploit new opportunities and markets.

A study by UNDP (2018) in Zambia found out that for the youth and women owned SMEs to succeed, special attention must be taken in training the SMEs on business planning, budgeting, and managerial processes. It was also revealed that most SMEs failed due to lack of knowledge and information to enable them to effectively plan, manage and make sound decisions to enhance the growth and survival of enterprises.

According to the exploration research done in Zambia by Mbuta (2007, p. 47) 15% of the respondents in the study did not get any entrepreneurship training, and of those who did, 75% (mean score 2.32) of the respondents do not attribute their

better sales to the entrepreneurship training they got. This is since prior findings indicated that SMEs had never received any entrepreneurial training. Most of them blamed their lack of training on a lack of knowledge, while others stated that the trainings are expensive, and they are unable to afford them.

2.4 The role of SMEs in the economy

Governments, worldwide, pay special attention to SME development as part of their employment strategy. They view SMEs as best able to create jobs for the vast majority of those in the labour market. They are seen as a vital part of the solution to the unemployment challenge Gregory et. al. (2005). Morrison et al. (2003). This viewpoint is borne out by the empirical evidence of how many of the people in the labour market are employed by SMEs. "In support of this, Morrison et al. (2003: p. 417) stated, "Policy interest in the small business sector stems from its capacity to provide and grow employment at local levels." Almost all African governments, including Kenya (2005), Tanzania (2003), Ethiopia (2008), South Africa (1996), and Zimbabwe (2003), have special policies for the development of SMEs based on their ability to alleviate unemployment. In support of this viewpoint, Rodrigues et. al. (2003: p289) observed that the importance of growth is also apparent in the preoccupation of the various administrations in developing an economic climate that favors corporate expansion. To this purpose, several policies have been devised with the goal of establishing a critical size that promotes competitiveness while lowering the death rate associated with small and medium-sized businesses. As a result, enterprise growth is regarded as a precondition for economic growth. SMEs are a vital tool for empowerment, equity, and redistribution, and are considered as both an indication of a solid economy and an essential condition for an economy to grow (Chamberlain and Smith, 2006).

SMEs are seen as a key vehicle for the empowerment of previously disadvantaged groups. This is particularly obvious in South Africa, where the growth of the SME sector is considered as a crucial vehicle for Black Economic Empowerment (BEE) by the South African Department of Trade and Industry (2005). Currently, Zambia has a dualistic economy which comprise of the formal manufacturing sector and the informal sector. The formal manufacturing sector of the economy employs 17% of the formal labour force (over 200 000 people) in approximately 40 000 enterprises. Most of these enterprises are SMEs with between 5 and 10 employees. The Zambian economy is based on Agriculture, Mining and Quarrying and Manufacturing which contributes approximately 21% to the GDP. The performance of the manufacturing sector has remained depressed registering an estimated GDP slump of 11% in 1994. GDP measures the total market value of all products and services produced within a country's boundaries over a certain time period. During the year 2000, manufactured exports accounted for 20% of total revenue. This situation is not sustainable, hence the need to increase production of value-added manufactures in the export basket (Central Statistical Office, 2010).

2.5 Theoretical framework

This study was guided by two theories: the knowledge-based theory an empowerment theory and training needs assessment theory.

2.5.1 Knowledge-based theory

This theory was first promoted by Penrose (1959). Barney (2001) and Conner (2001) later expanded it. KBT underline the significance empowerment through of knowledge acquisition. The theory argues that knowledge empowerment plays a dynamic role in increasing productivity of the SMEs and that of the economy (Romer, 2001). Therefore, SMEs and economies, with highly educated and trained manpower, are more likely to be of high performance compared to those that lack these key resources. The reason behind this notion is that well-educated and trained SMEs are quick at learning and applying new skills and proactive to develop efficiency, productivity, risk taking and innovativeness of the SME (Timmons, 2000).

Based on the context in which learning happens, the knowledge-based theory distinguishes between two types of learning. We have two types of learning: explorative learning, which comes from within the SME and can only happen through internal experimentation (Zahra, Nielsen, and Bogner, 2000) and is therefore experienced, and exploitative learning, which comes from outside the SME and must be acquired. Learning by doing is a fundamental process of knowledge development for entrepreneurs. Education may help students gain entrepreneurial skills and attitudes while also teaching them how to behave (Middleton, 2010). From a strategic point of view, an entrepreneur who has been trained could easily make the right decisions regarding which markets to enter, what product to produce and the selling prices (Hart, 2002). These decisions consistently differentiate between a high performing and low performing SME (Hart, 2002). Education and training therefore impinge upon analysis, planning, and control processes of the SME (Njoroge & Gathungu, 2013).

The entrepreneur's experience in acquiring, assimilating, and utilizing knowledge within and without the SME also influences entrepreneurial behavior. The capacity of an entrepreneur to innovate is determined by his or her prior experience. Entrepreneurs ordinarily abandon those ventures they have come to learn that they bear little returns and focus on those that promise the highest returns for a given level of risk. The information obtained via education and training determines a SME's ability to learn. The SME's level of innovation has an impact on the SME's experience. The SME's strategic stance and how it rejuvenates itself over time are determined by its experience (Kisaka,2014).

2.5.2 Training needs assessment theory

Kaufman and English were the first to create the training needs assessment hypothesis (1979). According to the notion, a true need can only be determined if it is not preceded by the selection of a solution. To conduct a quality needs assessment, first determine the present outcomes, then describe the intended goals. Consequently, the real requirement is defined as the difference between the present and intended results. Once a need has been recognized, a solution that is focused at addressing the gap can be chosen. A need, in the simplest sense, is a measurable gap between two situations, what is now and what should be, according to the theory. The evaluation process identifies problem areas, issues, or challenges that must be addressed.

According to Firdousi (2013) training needs assessment forms the most basic common forms of assessment used by human resource development professionals in the workplace. In this respect, needs assessment help to determine when training is needed and for whom. As a result, evaluation ensures that training programs are relevant to the individuals being trained. As a result, a training needs assessment offers the information required to build training programs. The main objective of a training needs assessment, according to Firdousi (2013), is twofold: first, to identify the knowledge and abilities that employees require to function well on the job, and second, to prescribe relevant interventions to fill these gaps. This is in keeping with Watkins and Kaufman's (2002) explanation that needs assessment include determining current circumstances, desired outcomes in the future, and a comparison of the two. As a result, needs assessment 22 entails making judgements about needs and prioritizing them to guide decisions about what to do next.

According to Goldstein (1991), needs assessment should be holistic in form to prevent misdiagnosing non-training issues as training issues. Hence, the process includes determining specific training needs of individuals in the firm or organization, and then selecting the most appropriate training content and delivery methods, evaluating the effectiveness of the training procedures before it is delivered. It can also be useful in analyzing the organizational context in terms of resources, management support, and other factors that may impede or help the successful implementation of a training effort.

To estimate SME performance, perceptual performance measures were used, which were based on self-reported ratings. Owner/managers were asked to rate the importance of each of the specified performance factors on a three-point scale ranging from 1 to 3, with 1 equaling "decreased" and 3 equaling "increased." Profit growth, sales growth, and productivity, average number of full-time and part-time employees, and customer happiness and loyalty were among the dimensions. As a result, training procedures, performance, benefits, and obstacles are used as keywords in this study.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

This study's framework examines the value of employee training to SMEs. In addition to budgetary constraints, information gaps cause smaller businesses to be less aware of the benefits of employee training, and few consider training as a strategic instrument. Small businesses may not reap the same benefits from training efforts as larger businesses due to higher staff turnover. In research, training practices in SMEs have gotten little attention. This study examines the state of staff training methods in SMEs, as well as the concerns and challenges that they face.

This study used perception measures created by Martell, Gupta, and Carroll (1996) in research on Human Resource Management techniques.

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Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of the Conceptual framework

2.7 Chapter Summary

This section described the literature that surrounds the research topic. It looked at the definition and concepts of Small and Medium Enterprises, the role they play in the economy as well as various viewpoints from different scholars on staff training in relation to the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises. The chapter also outlined the conceptual framework that has been adopted in the research study.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the research methodologies that will be used in the study. It provides details on the study design, study site and population, sample size and sampling procedure, data collection techniques and tools, and data analysis. It establishes the framework for data collection and analysis.

3.1 Research Design

This study will use a quantitative research design. Quantitative techniques will be used to determine the levels of awareness, influence and the types of training being conducted. This approach requires gathering statistical data that would be used to test the variables developed for this study. According to Cooper and Schindler (2011), quantitative data consists of responses that have been classified, categorized, and converted to numbers so that they may be manipulated for statistical analysis.

3.2 Research Site

The study will be conducted in Chongwe district of Lusaka province. Chongwe district is located in Lusaka province and has a population 141,301 (CSO 2010). SMEs located in the Chongwe mainly involved in the retail/ wholesale trade sector only.

3.3 Population of Study

According to Saunders (2007), the term population refers to the entire set of groups from which a sample is drawn. Therefore, the target population will comprise of will be SMEs in Chongwe District, registered under the Chongwe District Chambers of Commerce Trade and Industry. As a result, the acquired findings would be more representative, contributing to the findings' reliability and correctness.

3.4 Sampling Size

According to Kulbir (2003) a sample is a small proportion of a population selected for observation and analysis. It is a collection consisting of a part or subset of the object or individuals of population which is selected for the express purpose of presenting the population. The sample size calculation adds 10% to the sample size to account for respondents who the researcher is unable to contact or who refuse to participate.

The researcher will ensure that the chosen sampling interval will not hide a pattern. To determine an ideal sample size for each stratum and particularly SMEs, Slovin's formula will be used. This formula simplifies the calculation of sample sizes.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

The notation is such that:

- n is the desired sample size,
- N is the population size for SMEs in Chongwe district,
- e (being $\pm 10\%$) as Margin of error, and
- the Confidence Level is 90%

$$n = 1,000 / 1 + 1,000 \times 0.01$$

$$n = 1,000 / 10$$

$$n = 100$$

10% sample of $n = 100$ SMEs will be selected from the entire sampling frame of 1,000 SMEs from Chongwe districts registered with PACRA. Kothari and Garg, (2014) indicates that a sample size of 10% of a target population is considered large enough so long as it allows for reliable data analysis and allows testing for significance of differences between estimates. To select the sample, the researcher will collect a list of the registered SMEs that PACRA and the Municipal Council could give, together with contact details and email addresses.

3.5 Sample Technique

Purposive sampling will be used to pick respondents for the study. The researcher opted to use purposive sampling because it relies on the researcher's discretion to choose variables for the sample population (La Porta, et al. 2009). The entire sampling process will depend on the researcher's judgment and knowledge of the context hence help the researcher filter out irrelevant responses that do not fit into the context of the study.

3.6 Data collection method

In this study, the researcher will administer questionnaires as an instrument of data collection. Questionnaires are research tools which respondents are asked to respond to similar questions in a predetermined order (Gray, 2004). Questionnaires are relatively cheap as standardized questions and questions can be written for specific purposes. Use of questionnaires in data collection will help to ensure reliability and validity of the data collected to support the essay. Questionnaires will be framed according to the objectives of the research, which will be used as major themes. Each theme will have several constructs that were designed as a way of obtaining primary data so that measurable concepts/ variables can be captured.

3.7 Data analysis

Quantitative data from the survey questionnaire will be analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 22.0. The descriptive statistics for the demographic characteristics will run and the means and standard deviations for numeric variables will be processed. The analysis' principal goal will be to create descriptive statistics.

3.8 Instrument validity and reliability

According to Hambulo (2016) in quantitative models, bias and errors are easily determined by the power of the test called p value. In reducing them to a minimum level, the use of terms validity and reliability will be applied in this research. Stoep et al., (2009) defined reliability: "As the extent to which a measure yields the same scores across different times, groups of people, or versions of the instrument, in short, it's about consistency, and on the other hand a measure shows validity if it actually measures what it claims (or is intended) to measure or it is about truthfulness". Therefore, the researcher will consider the aspect of reliability and validity in the study. In reliability, the researcher will take measures.

The researcher will try to be clear to avoid ambiguity; observed standardization in questionnaire. The questionnaires will be administered to the respondents. The researcher will also take time to test it before the final data collection. The Cronbach coefficient alpha will be utilized to calculate the reliability using an inter-item consistency reliability test. The reliabilities should be more than 0.60 to be considered as a good measure of inter-item consistency reliability.

Validation will be taken care of by the researcher. The researcher will collect the data on his own making sure that everything was done in order. The researcher will be alive from formulation, administering the instruments. The uses of the data collection instrument will facilitate content validation because the research will cover adequately the important information needed in the study by lobbying for information from all the respondents selected purposively.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

According to Lincoln (2009), any research is never far from ethical issues and dilemmas. The researcher ensures that, the nature, purpose and benefit of the study was to be explained to the respondents before conducting survey. Informed and voluntary consent will be obtained from all the respondents before the distribution of the questionnaire by seeking from each participant. The researcher will build a rapport and credibility with respondents by respecting their rights to voluntarily participate or withdraw. Participants will be treated with dignity and respect, and they will be encouraged to disclose only what they are comfortable with. The researcher will be sensitive to the participants' biases, values, and personal interests in the issue and procedure. Further, they will be assured that their names would not be recorded and disclosed, but numbers would use for confidentiality's sake.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Introduction

A study on the role of entrepreneurship training in the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises was conducted in the month of July 2022 in Chongwe district. This study was premised on answering three research questions which are:

1. What types of training are being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs?
2. Are SMEs aware of trainings conducted in the area?
3. What is the influence of training programs on business growth of SMES in Chongwe district?

However, before presenting the findings, a demographic profile of respondents is presented.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the sample

This section gives an analysis, presentation and interpretation of respondents' gender, age, level of education, type of business, position held in the business and number of employees.

4.1.1 Gender demographics

The study intended to determine the gender of the respondents. (n = 90) of the respondents were SMES while n = 10 were key informants. The findings are presented in Figure 4.1. The gender distribution in the sample was dominated by males n = 84 (84.0%) as compared to females n = 16 (16.0%). This is an indication that there are more males owned enterprises compared to women. This confirms the findings of Farah (2014), who conducted research in Kenya and discovered that gender limits women's ability to accumulate social, cultural, human, and financial capital, as well as their ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities. In addition, most women who venture into businesses needed to be financed.

Figure 4.1: Sex of the respondents in % n = 100

4.1.2 Age of the respondents

In this study, there was rather uneven distribution of age among those that were (25 to 34) and (35 to 44) n = 46 (46.0%). The rest had paltry scores as shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Age

<i>Variable Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
18 to 24	2	2.0
25 to 34	46	46.0
35 to 44	46	46.0
45 to 54	5	5.0
55 and above	1	1.0

4.1.3 Level of education

The respondents were also required to state their highest level of educational qualification. Table 4.2 (a) shows the level of education of the respondents. It was interesting to learn that a significant number of the respondent had gone up to primary education n = 74 (74.0%), those that went to college/university n = 10 (10.0%). Therefore, majority of the respondents lack a sound academic background and as such do not run their businesses professionally. The findings are in congruent with a study done by Tripp (2009) who established low level of education provides low level self confidence in business growth.

Table 4:2 (a): Education level

<i>Highest level of education?</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Never been to school	7	7.0
Primary	74	74.0
Secondary	9	10.0
College/university	10	10.0

4.1.4 Types of Business

Table 4:2 (b): Type of business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Manufacturing	4	4.4	4.4	4.4
Service	17	18.9	18.9	23.3
trade	34	37.8	37.8	61.1
primary agriculture	35	38.9	38.9	100.0
Total	90	100.0	100.0	

The study revealed that the SMEs in the sample were engaged in n = 4 different types of business. The found that n = 35 (38.9%) were running their business on primary agriculture, n = 34 (37.8%) were engaged in trade business, n = 17 (18.9%) were doing service provision and n = 4 (4.4%) were involved in manufacturing business. From the data findings, the study found out that 33.4% of the respondents had been in their business for a period less than five (5) years and constituted the majority, 20.9% of the respondents had been in their business for a period of 11 to 15 years and 18.5% of the respondents had been in their businesses for over 16 years. This indicates that majority of the businesses had been in operation for less than 5 years.

4.1.5 Position held in the SME

Through this study, the researcher sought to establish the position held by the respondents in the business. The findings are presented in table 4.3. The result indicates that slightly over half of the respondents n = 48 (53.3 %) were the owners of the SME, n = 30 (33.3%) were employees, n = 6 (6.7%) of the respondents constituted of family members and n = 6 (6.7%) of the respondents were managers of the SMES. This shows that the majority of responders were business owners. From the findings, the study revealed that majority (77.1%) of the respondents had employed 0 to 19 employees, and only 0.3% had employed more than a hundred (100) employees.

Table 4.3: Position held in the SME

<i>Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	
	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Owner	48	53.3
Manager	6	6.7
Employee	30	33.3
Family member	6	6.7
Total	90	100.0

4.2 Awareness of trainings program

There was a contradiction of responses among the Key informant and the SMEs. When the SMEs were asked if they were aware of any entrepreneurial training programs in the area, majority of the respondents said no. Surprisingly, more than half of the respondents, $n = 80$ (88.9%), were unaware of any entrepreneurial training programs in the region, compared to $n = 11$ (11.0%) who were aware as shown in figure 4.1. Study found that there is a relatively low level of knowledge about the training programs available in the region. The findings support those of Regin (2017), who discovered that only SMEs with a high level of education participated in entrepreneurship training, whereas those without a high level of education did not due to a lack of interest or, in certain cases, a lack of understanding. It further concurs with Mayuran (2016) found that most SMEs do not participate in training programs due to a lack of information, since the majority of them are not learned and that there is a dearth of communication between training providers and SMEs hence, they are unable to participate in government-sponsored and partner-sponsored entrepreneurship training programs.

When the key informants were asked if there SMEs are aware entrepreneurship training programs offered in the district, interestingly, all of them $n = 10$ (100%) claimed that SMEs are aware about the training programs as shown in table 4.4. According to Committee of Donor Agencies for Small Enterprise Development, (2001) Governments, donors and private trainers have been actively involved in training, usually through public training institutions and publicly funded trainers. However, they find those means insufficient to attract fully the potential SMEs for entrepreneurship training. A study conducted in Brazil found that there is lack of communication between the Trainers and the prospective trainees, (Anderson 2000). This reduced the training awareness among SMEs across the country. According to FIT Resources Ltd (2002) Trainers often express their desire to use the media, but at the same time they think the media, such as radio and newspapers, are too expensive. This causes a vicious cycle, as marketing is not very efficient, there are fewer trainees than there might have been, then trainers may have to charge higher fees for training.

Table 4.4: Level of awareness about entrepreneurship training

SMEs	Frequency			
	Yes		No	
	n	%	N	%
Are you aware of any entrepreneurial training programs in your area?	80	88.9	10	11.1
Key Informants	n	%	N	%
Are SMEs aware of any entrepreneurial training programs in the area	10	100.0	.0	0.0

Source: Field data, 2022

The study also revealed that only $n = 6$ (6.7%) of the respondents in the sample had ever received entrepreneurship training as compared to $n = 84$ (93.3%) who did not. This is in strong agreement with Mayuran (2016) findings which establish that most SMEs do not participate in training programs. When asked how they would rate the cost of acquiring/pursuing entrepreneurial training. Most respondents (93.0%) thought it was expensive, while only 7% thought it was fair and cheap. These results are in line with FIT Resources Ltd (2002) who mentioned that as marketing is not very efficient, there are fewer trainees than there might have been, then trainers may have to charge higher fees for training. However, the key informants had different view about the cost of acquiring/pursing entrepreneurship training. Out of the 10 key informants who participated in the study, $n = 2$ (20%) said it was fair while $n = 8$ (80%) as the majority, said it was cheap. This concur with Anderson (2000) that there is lack of communication between the Trainers and the prospective trainees. This reduced the training awareness among SMEs across the country.

Table 4.5: Entrepreneurship training n = 100

<i>Have you ever received any entrepreneurship training?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Yes	6	6.7
No	84	93.3
In your opinion, how would you rate the cost of acquiring/pursuing entrepreneurial training? (SMEs)	n	%
Expensive	83	92.2
Fair	3	3.3
Cheap	4	4.4
In your opinion, how would you rate the cost of acquiring/pursuing entrepreneurial training? (Key informants)	N	%
Expensive	0	0.0
Fair	2	20.0
Cheap	8	80.0

4.3 Types of entrepreneurship training

The researcher sought to find the types of training being offered to SMEs in the region. The results are shown in the subsection below.

4.3.1 Business development training

Regarding business development training, a significant number of SMEs n = 80 (88.9%) didn't know these types of training while a paltry n = 10 (11.1%) knew. When the key informants were asked if they provided business development training, everyone in the study n = 10 (100%) agreed. This shows that there is a communication gap between the training providers and SMEs. See results in table 4.6. This is in line with Linan (2004) who indicated that this type of opportunity is useful for many SMEs and broadens their education to improve their business prospects. Secondly, entrepreneurship training to start a new business should be given to SMEs who have the inclination to start up a new venture

Table 4.6: Business development training

<i>What types of training are being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs?</i>	Frequency			
	Yes		No	
	N	%	N	%
Business development training (SME)	10	11.1	80	88.9
Business development training (KI)	10	100.0	0	0.0

4.3.2 Motivation and behaviour training

The study sought to establish if motivation and behaviour training were offered to SMEs in the region. There was no correlation between responses from the KI and SME. Most of the SMEs in the sample n = 80 (88.9%) didn't know these types of training while a paltry n = 10 (11.1%) knew. When the key informants were asked if they provided business development training, everyone in the study n = 10 (100%) in agreement. See results in table 4.7. This is in line with Fredrick, (2007) and Gatchalian, (2010) who established that in conveying entrepreneurial knowledge, skills and attitudes to learners, trainers use different types of training are offered based on the need or gap.

Table 4.7: Motivation and behaviour training

<i>What types of training are being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs?</i>	Frequency			
	Yes		No	
	N	%	n	%
Motivation and behaviour training (SME)	10	11.1	80	88.9
Motivation and behaviour training (KI)	10	100.0	0	0.0

4.3.3 Technical training

In terms of technical training, there was a disagreement response between the SMEs and the KI. Majority of the SMEs in the sample n = 80 (88.9%) didn't know these types of training while a trifling knew n = 10 (11.1%). When the key informants were asked if they provided business development training, everyone in the study n = 10 (100%) agreed.

Table 4.8: Technical training

<i>What types of training are being employed in Chongwe Based SMEs?</i>	Frequency			
	Yes		No	
	N	%	n	%
Technical training (SME)	10	11.1	80	88.9
Technical training (KI)	10	100.0	0	0.0

4.4 Influence of training programs on business growth of SMEs

There are several indicators on the influence of entrepreneurship training programs on business growth of SMEs. Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement that the indicators led to business growth of their SMEs using a Likert scale of 5- A lot larger, 4- A little larger, 3-No difference, 2- A little larger, 1- A lot larger. Table 4.9 shows the distribution of respondents on influence of the training program. Most of the Key Informants and SMEs in the sample were in a lot larger and little, larger agreement with positive statements about the Influence of training programs on business growth of SMEs. This is in concurrent with Jones (2005) who examined the influences of training towards enterprise growth confirmed that SMEs that increase training efforts managed to increase its growth in term of sales and revenues. The study conducted in Kenya by Moronge and Muiru (2013) also showed that training respondents rated programs as 15% excellent, 41% very good and 42% as good. The study therefore concluded that entrepreneurial training programs greatly contributed to the SMES growth. According to Gibb, (2002) entrepreneurial training is frequently seen as a response to the increasingly globalized, uncertain, and complex world we live in, requiring all people and organizations in society to be increasingly equipped with entrepreneurial competencies. Surlemont, (2007) also added that besides the common economic development and job creation related reasons, entrepreneurship training, increases SMEs' perceived relevancy, engagement, and motivation in both business and in work life

Table 4.9: Influence of training programs on business growth of SMEs in % n = 100

Statements	1	2	3	4	5
I believe training programs increases production	0	1	2	35	62
I believe training programs increases sales	0	1	2	37	60
I believe training programs creates employment	0	0	3	42	55
I believe training programs increase innovation	0	0	1	83	17
I believe training programs increase motivation and satisfaction	0	0	0	4	96
I believe training programs improve customer relations	0	0	11	16	73
I believe training programs creates more firm opportunities	0	0	14	20	66
I believe training programs improves performance in the business	0	1	2	42	55

The study found almost all the KI and SMEs in the sample n = 97 (97.0%) believes that entrepreneurship training programs increases production in the business a little larger and a lot larger while a trivial believes that there is no difference n = 2 (2.0%) and n = 1 (1.0%) believes that it contributes a little smaller. This indicates that training programs are influential in production increase of SMEs. Tan (2006) recorded those skills upgrading activities are vital and it could lead towards better productivity level and customer's satisfactions in the continent.

The study also revealed that 97 (97.0%) of the respondents strongly believes that training programs increases sales a little larger and a lot larger while an insignificant number of respondents felt that training contributes a little smaller n = 1 (1.0%) and n = 2 (2.0%) said felt there is no difference with or without the training. This is in good agreement with Tan (2006) recorded that training bring about sales increment, market share enlargement, and growth in demand.

On whether the training programs creates employment, majority of the respondent believed it does a little larger and a lot larger $n = 97$ (97.0%) while $n = 3$ (3.0%) did not perceive any difference. Governments, worldwide, pay special attention to SME development as part of their employment strategy. They view SMEs as best able to create jobs for the vast majority of those in the labour market. They are seen as a vital part of the solution to the unemployment challenge Gregory et. al. (2005) Morrison et al. (2003). This viewpoint is borne out by the empirical evidence of how many of the people in the labour market are employed by SMEs.

From the findings, all the KI and SMEs in the sample $n = 100$ (100%) indicated that training programs increases innovation in the business to a little and a lot larger. This means that SMEs who are trained are more likely to be more innovative than those that haven't been trained.

With regards to motivation and satisfaction, the study revealed that training programs motivates and makes the SMEs feel satisfied. In the study, all the respondents 100% expressed a strong agreement with the statement. Besides the common economic development and job creation related reasons to promote entrepreneurship training, entrepreneurial training can have on SMEs' perceived relevancy, engagement, motivation, and satisfaction in both business (Surlmont, 2007) and at work (Amabile and Kramer, 2011). In this study, most of the respondents $n = 82$ (82%) believed that entrepreneurship training improves customer relations while a few $n = 11$ (11.0%) did not see any difference. Tan (2006) confirms that skills upgrading activities among the top management of the companies in African countries are vital and it could lead towards better productivity level and customer's satisfactions in the continent. The latter then could bring about customers' loyalty.

The findings showed that 86% of the respondents agreed that training programs creates more firm opportunities while 14% did not see any difference with or without the training firms can have opportunities. This show that indeed when SMEs are trained, they are more likely to have new opportunities come their way.

The study results gave the impression that training programs improves performance in the business. Nearly all the respondents in the study 97% were of the view that once trained, SMEs are most likely to improve their performance as well as the business's. A measly disagreed with the statement. Mayuran (2016) conducted empirical research in South Africa on the influence of entrepreneurship training on small business performance and found that most people who receive training perform significantly well and improve their business.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter highlights all the key results obtained from respondents, as well as the conclusions drawn from the major findings and the researcher's suggestions based on the major findings and conclusions. The purpose of this study was to assess the role of entrepreneurship training in the growth of small and medium enterprises in Zambia: a case of Chongwe District

5.1 Conclusions of the study

The findings were consistent with literature findings by World Economic Forum (2009) which stated that entrepreneurial training was essential for skills development, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to create jobs, generate economic growth, advance human welfare, and stimulate innovation to address SMEs related economic challenges as this would be a catalyst for economic development.

The researcher sought to find out level of awareness among SMEs about training conducted in their areas. The study revealed that a significant of SMEs were not aware of the entrepreneurship trainings. This indicated that the level of awareness is rather low in the region.

The study sought to establish the types of training provided by the Key informants to the SMEs. It was noted that there was contradiction of responses between the two parties. Most of the SMEs did not know the types of training offered while the Key informants revealed that trainings were available for SMEs however, a significant of SMEs did not see the value of these trainings. This meant that there is information gap between them.

Finally, the correlation analysis to determine whether there was a significant relationship between training programs and business growth shows that a very strong relationship exists between the two variables. This implies that accessibility to training programs should be increases and any barriers to access training should be eradicated.

5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations made are confined to the role of entrepreneurial training on business growth of SMEs in Chongwe district. Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion made, the study makes the following recommendations:

1. There is need to provide awareness programs and well-established communication strategies to effectively reach out to all SMEs in the town and remote areas.
2. The Ministry of Community Development in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and donors should develop and implement a comprehensive curriculum on entrepreneurship education and training which should be integrated at all levels from nursery to university, to build a strong entrepreneurial culture early enough in the prospective SMEs.
3. The researcher recommends that there should be a well laid procedure on follow up process after the training to ensure that the SMEs have maximum benefit from the training programs

5.3 Suggestions for further study

1. This researcher takes exception to the fact that the study was conducted in Chongwe district. The researcher therefore suggests that the study be conducted in the whole of the country to determine the role of entrepreneurial training on business growth of SMEs.
2. The researcher suggests that a study should be conducted on the role of trainers in entrepreneurial training on business growth of SMEs.
3. The researcher further suggests that a study on the analysis of factors affecting business growth of SMEs under the devolved systems of government in Zambia.

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